

Colleges Of Education Students' Perception Of Teaching Practice Supervision And Teaching Effectiveness In Federal College Of Education (Technical), Omoku

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study was to investigate students' perception of teaching practice supervision and teaching effectiveness in the Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku, Rivers State. The study had four purposes, four research questions and four hypotheses were tested. The research design adopted for this study was the ex-post facto design. This study was conducted in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku, Rivers State. The population of the study consisted of all the 849 NCE three students of the 2022/2023 academic session of Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku, Rivers State. Accidental sampling method of the non-probability sampling technique was adopted for the study. The sample for the study consisted of three hundred (300) NCE three students who were on teaching practice. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled: "Students' Perception of Teaching Practice Supervision and Teaching Effectiveness Questionnaire" (SPTPSTEQ) which was administered through the help of the College Lecturers on Teaching Practice to the student-teachers in their respective schools. The hypotheses testing were done using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis (PPMC) technique and all the hypotheses were significant. Based on the findings it was concluded that the perceptions student-teachers hold about supervision goes a long way to affect their teaching effectiveness. It was recommended amongst other that supervisors should be cordial with student-teachers so as to enable them develop positive attitude towards teaching practice supervision to enable them improve on their performance.

Keywords: Students' perception, teaching practice supervision, teaching effectiveness

INTRODUCTION

Education is a vital tool in nation building. Teaching, however, is often rated high in the scheme of social services in most countries. Teachers themselves are the live-wire of any educational system. As such they are indispensable in nation building if any nation is to move forward. Teaching is a profession, and all forms of professional education have both theoretical and practical components.

If qualitative education is something to go by, good teaching is inevitable. This cannot be achieved unless teachers are carefully taught or trained, especially through teaching practice. Teaching practice is therefore the most important part of the teacher's professional training. It gives the teacher trainee the needed exposure to teaching. Therefore, to be regarded as a fully trained and qualified teacher, student-teachers must satisfy the requirement of practical teaching. This is to enhance their performance in the teaching subject and the theory of education (Lassa, 2001). Suffice it to say that teaching practice provides the appropriate classroom environment for transforming theories of teaching into practical experiences; it is therefore, an opportunity to put into practice various educational theories that the student teacher must have learnt.

According to Samuel and Vipene (2004), there are different functions that underlie the teaching practice exercise. These include to:

- i. Provide adequate field experience for professional development of student-teachers.
- ii. Provide opportunities for student-teachers to engage in a professional exercise in observing, sharing and participating in school activities and practical teaching.
- iii. Provide student trainees opportunities for translating theory into practice (Samuel et al., 2004, p.2).

Goldammer (2003) in recognition of the above advantages agrees that it is pertinent to note that "a teacher affects eternity, he can never tell where his influence stops" (p.2). A teacher needs to be properly groomed to enable him cultivate a positive attitude towards the profession. This positive attitude to the profession cannot be achieved if there is no supervision by a more experienced person. However, supervision is not new to the Nigerian educational system. Indeed it dates back to the time when schools were completely run by the missionaries. In the past, it was called inspection, but a conceptual shift was made from inspection to supervision. Ali (2008) defined supervision (both the teaching practice and real professional teachers) as a process of monitoring the activities of sub-ordinates in order to improve their performance or proficiency in their chosen area.

A further shift was made from mere supervision to what is today described as instructional supervision. The later is a set of supervisory activities that are designed to improve the teaching/learning process. The purpose is neither for the supervisor to pass judgment on the competence of teachers nor to control them, but rather it is for the supervisors to work co-operatively with them for the purpose of improving instruction (Oru & Ada, 2008). This kind of supervision embraces the curriculum and instructional matters and seeks to investigate how well teachers perform in their instructional roles. It finds out what teachers are supposed to teach, their particular content area and the effective methods and materials needed to impart desired skills, abilities, competencies and the behavior of teachers that are compatible with the goals of education. There is also the clinical supervision, which is the idea and effort put in by supervisors to help teachers upgrade their performance. It is based on data collected in actual classroom situations or other instructional situations directly with teachers and supervisors present as witnesses if not participants (Hoyle, 2007).

The supervision conference involves the convergence/meeting of supervisor with the supervisees in order for a verdict result of the supervision to be given or known and area of improvement specified. The post observation conference is the recapitulation stage by which the school leader or sectional head organizes to effectively point out the need and aspect for which the teacher needs improvement in order to effect better and higher learning outcome in the learners.

Based on the above assertions, coupled with personal observations of the researchers as discussed above, there is need to investigate students' perception of teaching practice supervision and teaching effectiveness in the Federal College of Education, Obudu, Cross River State becomes imperative.

Statement of the problem

According to Bassey and Archibong (2000); Okey and Archibong (2006), the standard of education at the primary and secondary school levels in Cross River State is steadily declining. Many factors have been attributed to this decline. Among them are school environment, parental or home background, students' poor attitude to study, lack of commitment on the part of teachers, poor motivation of teachers, fiscal constraints, and lack of effective supervision of teachers particularly teachers-in-the-making (student-

teachers). These have been regarded as most vital and most inimical to the development of both primary and secondary education. For the student-teacher to be effective in the teaching profession he or she has to learn and practice the rudiments of teaching. Supervision of teachers is a continuous process of assisting teachers, particularly student-teachers to attain professionalism. This will enhance feedback, which will help them improve the instructional effectiveness.

One important condition for teaching to take place is that the teacher, at least, assumes that he/she is more knowledgeable than the person he is teaching. Thus, to be able to bring about learning, the teacher should know what teaching involves, what content he wants his learners to master, and various approaches he has to evolve to facilitate the mastery. This condition makes it mandatory that student-teachers should be exposed to practical teaching exercise to enable them meet the above conditions. Unfortunately, most student-teachers lack the knowledge of the subject, the necessary skills, appropriate methodology to be applied in order to facilitate teaching and learning. The problem of the study therefore is to investigate students' perception of teaching practice supervision and teaching effectiveness of NCE students Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku, Rivers State.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate students' perception of teaching practice supervision and teaching effectiveness among NCE students of Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku, Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Examine the extent to which students' perception of teaching practice supervision relate with teaching effectiveness.
2. Ascertain the extent to which students' perception of lesson notes evaluation relate with teaching effectiveness.
3. Determine the extent to which students' perception of the use of instructional materials relate with teaching effectiveness.
4. Find out the extent to which students' perception of teaching practice preparation relate with teaching effectiveness.

Research questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study:

1. To what extent does students' perception of teaching practice supervision relates with their teaching effectiveness?
2. How does students' perception of lesson notes evaluation relates with their teaching effectiveness?
3. To what extent does students' perception of the use of instructional materials relates with their teaching effectiveness?
4. How does students' perception of teaching practice preparation relates with their teaching effectiveness?

Research hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between students' perception of teaching practice supervision and teaching effectiveness.
2. There is no significant relationship between students' perception of lesson notes evaluation and teaching effectiveness.
3. There is no significant relationship between students' perception of the use instructional materials and teaching effectiveness.
4. There is no significant relationship between students' perception of teaching practice preparation and teaching effectiveness.

Literature review

Students' Perception of Teaching Practice Supervision and Teaching Effectiveness

Teaching can be defined as giving lessons to students in an institution of learning. It can also be defined as showing students how to do something so that he/she will be able to do it (Hornby, 2006). Therefore

teachers are expected to tailor their teaching to meet the learner's level and use their daily routine experiences and activities to help them learn. Academically and professionally qualified teachers are expected to dedicate a lot of their time and effort to develop and reinforce their students' creative thinking. This creates in the learners positive attitudes towards what is being taught, demonstrated and illustrated regardless of its challenges.

Teaching practice provides an opportunity for student-teachers to put into practice these skills before they begin to work as professionals. In another study by Alnaji (2000) who conducted a survey of graduates in various specializations on the importance of teaching skills and the extent to which they acquired them in teaching practice at Mu'tah University. The findings indicated that the extent to which the graduates acquired such skills was moderate. Jackson (2002) conducted a study on student-teachers' attitudes towards teaching practice and supervisors as critical in determining the extent to which the trainees get involved in the teaching process. The study found that student-teachers' attitudes towards the following were positive: supervisor, time allocated for training, the extent of follow up by supervisor and having more than one cooperating teacher.

Students' Perception of Lesson Notes Evaluation and Teaching Effectiveness

The influence of supervisors and evaluation of teachers' performance has been intensively investigated. Joshua (2004) carried out a study to determine the attitude of secondary school teachers towards principals' evaluation of their teaching instructional techniques in Cross River State. He used a 50 item instrument with a four-point Likert scale-type to gather data from 1500 teachers. The generated data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and one-way analysis of variance statistical techniques. Results revealed that about 60 percent of the teachers sampled scored above average (50 to 66% marks) on their attitude towards principals' evaluation of their instructional techniques. Those who scored below average indicated that their instructional techniques did not correlate with the academic performance of students.

Mboto (2005) conducted a study to determine the attitude of primary school teachers to evaluation of their instructional effectiveness in the Central Senatorial District of Cross River State. After data analysis, it was found out that teachers who passed through Teachers' Training Colleges cultivated more positive attitude, and were always more serious in the performance of their duty than their counterpart who did not pass through Teacher Training Colleges, but possess NCE certificates.

Students' Perception of the Use of Instructional Materials and Teaching Effectiveness

Umoren (2004) defined instructional materials as those facilities, equipment and materials utilized by a teacher to illustrate, emphasize and explain a lesson with the intention of making the lesson clearer and captivating to the learners. Uche and Erukoha (2004) found out that some student-teachers develop negative attitude to the use of teaching materials when they do not understand, or have no good knowledge of the equipment or instructional materials in question. He therefore, advised that student-teachers should ensure that they have a good knowledge of the material before using it to teach. In line with the above Nworji (2002) found out in his study that the more student-teachers are subjected to supervision, the more positive attitude they would develop towards the use of teaching instructional materials during and after their teaching practice exercise.

Students' Perception of Teaching Practice Preparation and Teaching Effectiveness

The teacher educators have the duty of making adequate arrangement in terms of learning contents, methodology and evaluation in the preparation of their students for such a programme. The students must be adequately exposed to courses that will enhance their performances on the field. Study by Nworji (2002) indicated that learning to translate one's knowledge of a subject area into subject content is one of the important and difficult things which student-teachers have to know. Uche and Erukoha (2004) studied on the influence of student-teacher's attitude on preparation before teaching and its effects on the students' teaching practice exercise. He argued that the act of preparation is the key to a teacher's successful teaching of his/or lesson in the classroom. In a study to determine the effect of attitudes towards preparation before actual lesson.

METHODOLOGY

THE research design adopted for this study was the ex-post facto design. This study was conducted in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku, Rivers State. The population of the study consisted of all the eight hundred and forty-nine (849) NCE three of the 2022/2023 academic session of Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku, Rivers State (Teaching Practice Unit, Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku, Rivers State). Accidental sampling method of the non-probability sampling technique was adopted for this study. The sample for the study consisted of three hundred (300) NCE three students randomly drawn from a total population of 849 NCE three NCE students who were on teaching practice. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled: “Students’ Perception of Teaching Practice Supervision and Teaching Effectiveness Questionnaire” (SPTPSTEQ) which was administered through the help of the College Lecturers on Teaching Practice supervision to the student-teachers in their respective schools. The hypotheses testing were done using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis (PPMC) technique. All the hypotheses were tested at the 5% level of significance.

RESULTS

Hypothesis one: There is no significant relationship between students’ perception of teaching practice supervision and teaching effectiveness.

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the relationship between students’ perception of teaching practice supervision and teaching effectiveness N=300

Variable	$\sum x$ $\sum y$	$\sum x^2$ $\sum y^2$	$\sum xy$	r-cal
Students’ perception of teaching practice supervision	3897	52125	52848	0.804*
Teaching effectiveness	3981	54153		

* Significant at .05, critical r = .178, df = 298

The obtained r-value was 0.804. This value was tested for significance. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected because the calculated r-value of the 0.804 is found to be greater that the critical r-value of 0.178 at 0.05 probability level, and with 298 degrees of freedom. This result means that there is a significant relationship between students’ perception of teaching practice supervision and teaching effectiveness.

Hypothesis two: There is no significant relationship between students’ perception of lesson notes evaluation and teaching effectiveness.

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the relationship between students’ perception of lesson notes evaluation and teaching effectiveness N=300

Variable	$\sum x$ $\sum y$	$\sum x^2$ $\sum y^2$	$\sum xy$	r-cal
Students’ perception of lesson notes evaluation	3888	52032	52659	0.722*
Teaching effectiveness	3981	54153		

* Significant at .05, critical r = .178, df = 298

The obtained r-value was 0.722. This value was tested for significance. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected because the calculated r-value of the 0.722 is found to be greater that the critical r-value of 0.178 at 0.05 probability level, and with 298 degrees of freedom. This result means that there is a significant relationship between students’ perception of lesson notes evaluation and teaching effectiveness.

Hypothesis three: There is no significant relationship between students’ perception of the use instructional materials and teaching effectiveness.

Table 3: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the relationship between students’ perception of the use instructional materials and teaching effectiveness N=300

Variable	$\sum x$ $\sum y$	$\sum x^2$ $\sum y^2$	$\sum xy$	r-cal
Students’ perception of the use instructional materials	3761	48852	50640	0.482*
Teaching effectiveness	3981	54153		

* Significant at .05, critical r = .178, df = 298

The obtained r-value was 0.482. This value was tested for significance. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected because the calculated r-value of the 0.482 is found to be greater than the critical r-value of 0.178 at 0.05 probability level, and with 298 degrees of freedom. This result means that there is a significant relationship between students’ perception of the use instructional materials and teaching effectiveness.

Hypothesis four: There is no significant relationship between students’ perception of teaching practice preparation and teaching effectiveness.

Table 4: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the relationship between students’ perception of teaching practice preparation and teaching effectiveness N=300

Variable	$\sum x$ $\sum y$	$\sum x^2$ $\sum y^2$	$\sum xy$	r-cal
Students’ perception of teaching practice preparation	3849	50913	52257	0.829*
Teaching effectiveness	3981	54153		

* Significant at .05, critical r = .178, df = 198

The obtained r-value was 0.829. This value was tested for significance. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected because the calculated r-value of the 0.829 is found to be greater than the critical r-value of 0.178 at 0.05 probability level, and with 98 degrees of freedom. This result means that there is a significant relationship between students’ perception of teaching practice preparation and teaching effectiveness.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Students’ perception of teaching practice supervision and teaching effectiveness

The result of the first hypothesis revealed that there was a significant relationship between students’ perception of teaching practice supervision and teaching effectiveness. The finding of this study is in consonance with Alnaji (2000) who found that the extent to which the graduates acquired such skills was moderate. The finding is also supported by Jackson (2002) whose study found that student-teachers’ attitudes towards the following were positive: supervisor, time allocated for training, the extent of follow up by supervisor and having more than one cooperating teacher.

Students’ Perception of Lesson Notes Evaluation and Teaching Effectiveness

The result of the second hypothesis revealed that there was a significant relationship between students’ perception of lesson notes evaluation and teaching effectiveness. The finding is in line with Mbotto (2005) who found out that teachers who passed through Teachers’ Training Colleges cultivated more positive attitude, and were always more serious in the performance of their duty than their counterpart primary schools teachers who did not pass through Teacher Training Colleges, but possess NCE certificates. It is also in agreement with Umoren (2004) who supported that some teachers are incompetent as secondary school tutors (even though they possessed higher education in the science subjects that they teach).

Students’ Perception of the Use of Instructional Materials and Teaching Effectiveness

The result of the third hypothesis revealed that there was a significant relationship between students’ perception of the use of instructional materials and teaching effectiveness. The finding is in line with the study by Uche and Erukoha (2004) which found out that some student-teachers develop negative attitude

to the use of teaching materials when they do not understand, or have no good knowledge of the equipment or instructional materials in question.

Students' perception of teaching practice preparation and teaching effectiveness

The result of the fourth hypothesis revealed that there was a significant relationship between students' perception of teaching practice preparation and teaching effectiveness. The finding is in line with Nworji (2002) who argued that the act of preparation is the key to a teacher's successful teaching of his/or lesson in the classroom. It is also in line with Joshua (2004) who found out that about 98 percent of student-teachers (used as sample) showed positive attitude towards pre-lesson preparation.

CONCLUSION

From the results of the findings of this study and other relevant literature it can be concluded that the perception student-teachers hold about supervision goes a long way to affect their teaching effectiveness.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Supervisors should be cordial with student-teachers so as to enable them develop positive attitude towards teaching practice supervision to enable them improve on their effectiveness.
2. Student-teachers should be encouraged through financial stipends to enable them to purchase and use instructional materials that relate to the various lessons both during teaching practice and thereafter, so as to better complement their lessons.
3. Student-teachers should continue to prepare their notes of lesson before teaching to make them more efficient on the job.
4. Supervisors should take time to engage student-teachers on post evaluation supervision forum after the supervision exercise, so as to give them positive encouragement on the job/profession.

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